

Research Data in the Fraunhofer Digital Project : Creating a FAIR Research Data Infrastructure and Culture

Oya Beyan ¹, Andrea Wuchner ², Dirk Eisengräber-Pabst ², Christoph Quix ¹,
Christian Zäschke ³, Oliver Schumacher ⁴

¹ Fraunhofer FIT, Germany {[beyan.christoph.quix](mailto:beyan.christoph.quix@fit.fraunhofer.de)}@fit.fraunhofer.de; ² Fraunhofer IRB, Germany {[andrea.wuchner](mailto:andrea.wuchner@irb.fraunhofer.de),
[dirk.eisengraeber-pabst](mailto:dirk.eisengraeber-pabst@irb.fraunhofer.de)}@irb.fraunhofer.de; ³ Fraunhofer IOSB, Germany, christian.zaschke@iosb.fraunhofer.de;

⁴ Fraunhofer , Germany oliver.schumacher@zv.fraunhofer.de

Abstract

The Fraunhofer Society, as the leading organization for applied research in Europe, conducts its research activities at 72 institutes and research units at locations throughout Germany. The Fraunhofer Digital project, a part of the Fraunhofer 2022 Agenda, introduces the vision that research and administrative data will be linked, aggregated and analyzed in order to optimize research and development processes and support management decisions. As a part of this vision, the Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space project develops methods to reuse the research data in a broader sense and integrate research data silos in various institutes into Fraunhofer Data Space. In this work, we present the concept, early outcomes, and a FAIRness assessment of the research data repository approach. In our assessment, we used the FAIR metrics, and as a result developed a set of recommendations. These recommendations will be utilized to establish a digital research data infrastructure as well as a research data reuse culture in Fraunhofer. They can be also useful for other large scale institutions with heterogeneous research communities.

Keywords

Research Data Infrastructure; Data reuse; Fraunhofer Data Space; FAIR evaluation

I. Introduction

The Fraunhofer Society is the largest organization for applied research and development services in Europe, with 72 institutes and research units spread throughout Germany, each focusing on different fields, predominantly in natural science or engineering studies. The majority of the more than 25 000 staff are qualified scientists and engineers who work with an annual research budget of 2.3 billion euro. Since 2006, the Fraunhofer Society has adopted the open access policy that implies granting free and long-term access to scientific findings and scientific literature. In recent years, an agenda for open data has been established, and starting in 2015, a research data management and an infrastructure project has been launched [1]. The Fraunhofer Institutes are largely independent in their research project planning and implementation. Therefore, the research data generated by different research communities is stored and maintained in heterogeneous repositories without any standard ways of access [2]. Although there are versatile networks, they currently do not support the discoverability, accessibility, and reusability requirements of open science.

The need to have an overarching research data infrastructure is addressed by the Fraunhofer Digital project. As part of the Fraunhofer 2022 Agenda, research data and administrative data will be annotated, linked, aggregated, and analyzed in order to optimize the research and development processes and support management decisions in the institutes and in central levels. The envisioned infrastructure will enable the creation and maintenance of research data objects, as well as support data analytics workflows. This paper will present the initial result of the Fraunhofer Digital project concept phase for research data. Currently, the overall system is mainly at the conceptual design phase. However, certain components of the system are already in use or at the implementation phase. The bibliographic database publica and the open access repository ePrints already serve the Fraunhofer society as a platform to share research publications. The FORDATIS project started at 2016 aims to develop a research data repository, and is in implementation phase. The following section will introduce the concept and the projects which are a part of the research data

infrastructure. The subsequent section will present an assessment of the designed system relative to the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data. Finally, we will discuss a set of recommendations that developed as results of our assessment which serve the establishment of a data sharing culture and infrastructure in large scale research institutions with decentralized heterogeneous research activities.

II. Research Data in the Fraunhofer Digital Project

The Fraunhofer Digital project is part of the Agenda 2022 which aims to provide an efficient IT infrastructure to support the emerging needs of research and innovation as well as digital business processes. It is a cross departmental project which involves six Fraunhofer institutes, and it is composed of three main sub project aims: (i) to modernize the current automation of business processes, (ii) to make diverse Fraunhofer data sources available in Fraunhofer Data Space, and (iii) to develop a business intelligence framework to enable the linking, aggregating, analysis, and presentation of data.

Figure 1 presents an overall view of the Fraunhofer Digital Project. The IT infrastructure will support processes from data generation to data analysis to create machine processable and reusable data objects. The business intelligence layer will be based on two main types of data sources. The first is the administrative data generated by Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems (the left side of the figure). Currently Fraunhofer administrative processes are mainly executed through an IT system called SIGMA. There are also independent Data Management Systems (DMS) implemented for specific tasks. The right part of Figure 1 displays the sources of the research data, which is the focus of the “Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space” project. This project is one of the sub projects that constitutes the Fraunhofer Digital Project. It targets the development of methods of reusing the research data in a broader sense, and integrating research data silos residing in Fraunhofer Institutes into Fraunhofer Data Space. The current Fraunhofer research data landscape is composed of a centralized system for publication data, a centralized patent and intellectual property (IP) management system, and diverse systems which are owned and governed by research communities distributed over 60 Fraunhofer institutes. As conceptualized in Figure 1, the digital infrastructure will integrate the data generated in various systems into databases, and will provide business intelligence to analyze them.

Fig1: The Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space as part of the Fraunhofer Digital project

In the “Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space” project, the Fraunhofer Industrial Data Space will serve as a virtual secure data space for facilitating the exchange and linking of research data by providing standards and common governance models [3]. It will contain separately maintained research data sources, both centralized and decentralized. Research data will be semantically described, and it will be discoverable and accessible. The Fraunhofer reference architecture model [4] will be the base for describing research data assets, and it will be extended with required additional semantics. Connectors will be used to integrate data silos, whereas data apps will extend their functionalities with customized data integration, processing, linking, and publishing. Brokers will enable the interaction between data consumers and data providers in a secure environment. The project also

has a view to sharing data between federated research data infrastructures by establishing consortia of data owners and infrastructure managers.

The project is divided into three phases, namely: analysis and concept; realization and implementation; and operation and further development. The concept phase, which started in 2018, has two main goals: (i) to identify representative use cases on how research data is generated, stored, and reused; and (ii) a prototypical implementation of an expandable core of Fraunhofer Data Space, covering a broad, representative selection of research data sources. This implementation, as a proof of concept, will verify the developed concepts and help to evaluate conformance with existing and emerging research data management standards and recommendations, such as Horizon 2020, for data management plans or European Open Science Cloud.

As a cross institutional project, the “Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space” project is built upon ongoing projects and works carried out by participating Fraunhofer institutions. One of these is the extension of existing open access publication repositories, Publica and ePrints, which are the official institutional repositories of the Fraunhofer society for sharing research publications. The second is the FORDATIS project, which was started in 2016 as a part of the Fraunhofer Open Access Strategy 2020, with the goal of building a research data repository. The project is part of the EU-Horizon 2020 project JERRI [1] and has been designed to create a meta-level describing research data and data management plans. Other relevant work involves data and metadata modelling as part of the Fraunhofer Industrial Data Space project. The following subsections will give an overview of the existing projects and works, and will present their vision to support the Fraunhofer Digital research data concept and infrastructure.

A. Publication Data Infrastructure

The Fraunhofer Publication Infrastructure began as a bibliographic database and was complemented in 2003 by an Open-Access (OA) Repository. Today, the Publication Infrastructure (Publica and ePrints) serves an output of over 10,000 scientific papers, books, and conference papers published every year. The growing OA Repository is fostered by a top-down OA-Strategy, an OA Publication fund, and an OA-transformation task force. It is the data fundament for all services managed by the “Research Service & Open Science” Team (RSOS).

In the context of the project “Fraunhofer Digital”, Publica and ePrints will be updated to a new technological platform. It will become the principle system for Fair Data Sharing of all Fraunhofer OA-Disseminates – including research data, scientific software, patents etc.. Disseminates like research data will not have to be held in the system itself, but their metadata will. The wide diversity of resources will be linked to further entities of the research ecosystem like projects and researchers.

The new machine-friendly Fraunhofer Publica will be more research and resource centric as part of a globally networked research community. It will also provide automated processes and workflows to support researchers during the publication process. The Business Intelligence Ready Publica will not only act as first point of contact to the Fraunhofer Open Science Cloud, it will also serve as a data source for Fraunhofer internal data handling.

B. The FORDATIS Research Data Repository

The FORDATIS Research Data Infrastructure project was started by the Fraunhofer Society with the goal of complementing the existing publication infrastructure and related services with a Fraunhofer Research Data Repository named “FORDATIS”. FORDATIS supports the vision of making the results of publicly funded projects freely available to the public on a long-term basis, in order to make it possible to verify research results and make data more useful for further research. Funding organizations and science policy initiatives promote open research data such as the Horizon 2020 EU Open research data pilot, and they provide guidelines for best practice to make data available, e.g., the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. To fulfill these requirements, the FORDATIS project has set the following goals for published research data: (i) the construction of a research data repository to centrally record research data and provide it for reuse; (ii) the integration of the research data repository into national and international structures (e.g., OpenAIRE platform, European Open Science Cloud EOSC, Re3Data, Base); (iii) the implementation of a DOI-Assignment in order to make the research data uniquely identifiable and citable; and (iv) the establishment and development of a permanent centralized service to ensure persistent access to data.

The first step in the implementation was the development of an application profile containing all the metadata fields to describe research objects, namely both research data and software object types. The developed profile complies with EU and DOI requirements. The application profile is based on the DataCite-Standard version 4.0 [5]. In the next step, we realized that various objects, such as author and project, originally intended as attributes of the resource "research data", were also relevant for publications that are stored within the Fraunhofer Publica. Ideally, these data should be collected as separate objects with their own key and linked to publications and research data. Therefore, the data models are revised according to these requirements (Figure 2).

At the current state of the project, the implementation choices are being discussed. The repositories DSpace 6.x and DSpace Cris are considered possible choices [6] [7]. Both systems are open source with a large developer community and are already being used as research data repositories in other institutions. Since the FORDATIS repository should be integrated into the existing publication infrastructure, the final implementation choice will depend on the design choices of the Publica and ePrints systems.

Figure 2: FORDATIS/Publica-Object-Model

C. Research Data Provenance and Research Objects Metadata

One of the challenges of integrating the research data into Data Space is identifying and understanding the original sources of research data. As in almost every research organization, this is also a very heterogeneous structure in Fraunhofer, including file systems, database systems, or proprietary data stores of specific applications (e.g., control software of a measurement device in a lab). To obtain an overview of the available research data sources and the research objects contained in them, we are currently using questionnaires to collect the basic information. The collected information will be formalized in a metamodel which is based on the Information Model of the Industrial Data Space (IDS) [8].

However, the current work covers only the descriptive and administrative metadata of the research data. To enable interoperability of the research data, we also need to capture the structural metadata. The structural metadata describes the structure of the data containers and also contains the schema of a relational database or XML document, the tree structure of a JSON document, or just a list of columns of a CSV file. This information can then be used by data integration systems to exchange data between different organizational units. As it is already available in the data containers, this metadata can be extracted automatically from the sources [9].

In the next phases of the project, we plan to make the metadata available in a comprehensive metadata management system, which allows the curation, semantic enrichment and the annotation of the extracted metadata.

D. Long Term Archiving

In addition to the process of persisting and describing data using metadata, a long-term archiving concept for the Research Data must be elaborated. It is necessary to consider which data needs to be archived in which way. In addition, the process of accessing archived data has to be described. At the current state of the project, long term archiving concept is under development.

To make data searchable and retrievable by different communities working in various domains, domain specific metadata must be provided. Such specific metadata enables the provision of the relevant data to the requester in an efficient way. To allow this, it is first necessary to determine the right set of metadata for a specific community. Subsequently we need to extract this information from the existing research data and its corresponding metadata and make it available for the search and retrieval functionality.

When working with data, access restrictions must also be taken into account. Some data might be of interest for different persons working in the same or in different institutions. So it would be very useful if those persons could easily access this data. On the other hand, if this data is sensitive in some kind of way (e.g., personal or security-related data,) there needs to be protective measures to restrict access to this data. Therefore, the concept should also allow easy access for authorized persons and effectively protect the data as needed.

In the long term, metadata models are subject to change. This change also affects long-term archiving. If such change emerges, conversion strategies must be applied. One solution could be to transform the queries performed on the data storage which would mainly affect the intermediate layer between the requester and the storage. Another way could be to change the data representation on the storage side which would imply changes in the data storage level. In this project, we will investigate the best approach for the Fraunhofer environment.

III. FAIRness Assessment of the Fraunhofer Research Data Repository

One of the targets of the concept phase of the project is to evaluate the Fraunhofer research data management approach in terms of best practice, recommendations, and guidelines. FAIR principles provide guidelines for making digital research objects findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, both for machines and humans. The goal of the Research Data in the Fraunhofer Data Space project is to enable business intelligence to consume research data without any additional manual processes. Therefore, to evaluate compliance with the FAIR principles in the early stages of the project, it was important to provide feedback on the conceptual approach. With this early feedback, the overall approach will be revised, and the project goals could also be revised.

Figure 3. The FAIR Metrics fulfillment level

We assessed the design principles and implementation choices regarding the FAIR principles and identified challenges and recommendations. Although the FAIR principles are well known, the metrics to measure FAIRness are still in progress. Recently, a definition of the FAIRness measurement was published by the FAIR Metrics group. The group developed a framework and a core set of FAIRness indicators [10]. In our work we used 14 exemplary universal metrics, developed by this group, covering each of the FAIR sub-principles¹. A summary matrix of the evaluation outcome is presented in Figure 3. Fully satisfied metrics are colored green, partially satisfied ones, yellow, and failed ones, red.

Metrics addressing the findability aspects are fully satisfied by the Fraunhofer Research Data infrastructure. The FORDATIS system implements DOIs as persistence identifiers and machine readability of the data is ensured by application profiles in Dublin Core format. The application profile provides dedicated fields to include the DOI of the data it describes. DSpace Lucene solutions will ensure the indexing of the metadata in searchable resources. One of the shortcomings of the current implementation is that it only supports high level metadata of research objects.

Accessibility principles are only partially satisfied. Our approach implements open protocols and provides access authorization and authentication. However, there is not yet a policy defined to describe processes and mechanisms to access restricted content. Therefore, the access authorization metric is only partially satisfied. Another failure point is related to metadata longevity solutions. The current implementation does not have a metadata longevity approach. This shortcoming will be addressed in collaboration with the long-term archiving group.

Interoperability metrics aim to evaluate unambiguous communication of both metadata and data. The FORDATIS system follows best practice regarding metadata. Data resources are described with formal and accessible knowledge representation language and vocabulary. However, no mechanism exists to monitor how individual data sets satisfy these metrics. The current application profile supports qualified references, linking metadata to the data sets.

Reusability evaluation measures the existence of a usage license, availability of detail provenance, and certification of resources. Since no certification body exists yet, last metric is unachievable for any data infrastructure. Creative common licenses are used by the FORDATIS system. The system keeps provenance information via Dublin Core vocabulary such as creator, publisher, description and dates. However, there is no contextual provenance related to why and how data is produced.

IV. Discussion and Recommendations

As the outcome of the assessment of the Fraunhofer Digital Research Data concept and implementation choices with FAIR principles, a set of recommendations have been developed. In our evaluation we observed that FAIR metrics were not always sufficient to measure progress through machine processable research data objects. In many cases, although the current FAIR metrics are satisfied, recommendations are given for achieving widespread adaptation of the research data reuse culture.

The Fraunhofer society, with over 60 institutions, embraces many scientific communities with different needs and requirements. The following recommendations were developed to assist a research data infrastructure which strives to support a variety of use cases arising from these communities. The future adaptation of requirements will guide the Fraunhofer society in implementing an infrastructure which will support the creation and maintenance of a citable, shareable research data object for reusable and reproducible science.

Rec 01 - Persistence Policy and Related Services : The FORDATIS system has a persistence identifier system based on DOIs. However, it is important to understand the advantages and limitations of different identifier schemas. Researchers may have diverse needs and they may need guidance to identify the right PID schemas; and in some cases they may need support to establish different PID schemas for their projects. Fraunhofer can provide guidelines, consultancy support, and a PID system as a service.

¹ <http://htmlpreview.github.io/?https://github.com/FAIRMetrics/Metrics/blob/master/ALL.html>

Rec 02 - Research Data Policies: Research data policy documents describes policies, terms of use, and guidelines for the reuse of data. Fraunhofer research communities have their own approach and restrictions regarding data reuse policies. However, identifying these requirements and harmonizing heterogeneous policies at the institutional level is a challenging task. An institutional data policy framework can ensure coherence across community level data policies. A policy registry system and related services can help researchers to specify their own data reuse policies and link with the institutional strategies. A common structure of policies and guidelines to customize the specifications and semantic annotation capabilities can help researchers to develop and publish their data plans.

Rec 03 - Rich and Machine-readable Metadata: The current practice of machine-readable metadata is limited with high level descriptions of research data sources. Most of the context specific information captured in description fields is in a natural language. Since metadata curation is time-consuming, the only way to achieve desired rich metadata is the extensive use of automated tools. Fraunhofer can support researchers by investing in tools to capture and formalize metadata data as a part of their daily activities. These tools, coupled with the project management and data stewardship workflow, can enable Fraunhofer researchers to generate machine readable semantic metadata, and can optimize the business processes of creation and publishing of the metadata. The new generation machine executable data management plans and their supporting tools might be considered as a solution.

Rec 04 - Metadata Longevity Plan: As part of preservation policy, a long term archiving strategy and metadata longevity plan should be developed. These plans should include items such as policy and procedures for digital archiving, backup schedules, and preservation of fair objects.

Rec 05 - Research Data Objects: The scope of the research data objects should be defined. Data, metadata, algorithms, materials, or hardware can be considered as research data. The knowledge representation language and supported data types should be identified.

Rec 06 - Licensing: A rich option of data licensing should be provided for researchers, including creating their own licenses. Guidance for selecting the right licenses should be provided.

Rec 07 - Contextual Provenance: Contextual provenance is important for the reuse of the data. It defines the context the data is produced in and the relevance of the data for the reuse purpose. This metadata can be used to evaluate the quality or fitness for the use from the perspective of the data consumer. However, it is challenging to define the scope of the context and methods for collecting metadata. Different research communities may have different needs and perspectives regarding the context. A community-driven approach can be adopted, and contextual provenance can be prototyped in selected use cases.

Rec 08 - Data quality: High quality research data is a cornerstone of scientific knowledge. FAIR principles provides only limited guidelines regarding the quality of the data itself. New standards for the measurement of the data quality should be studied.

V. Conclusion

The Fraunhofer Digital Research Data project develops a research data infrastructure to integrate and link heterogeneous research data repositories to the Fraunhofer Data Space. The framework will support business intelligence as well as the reuse of data. The project is in the conceptual phase and is composed of multiple projects executed by different institutions from the Fraunhofer society.

This paper presents the Fraunhofer approach to research data infrastructure, and it reports the outcome of a self-assessment of current design and implementation choices with FAIR metrics. As a result of the self-assessment, a set of recommendations were developed, and the feedback was provided to the conceptual design.

The Fraunhofer Institute, as a large scale distributed research organization, could potentially play a leading role in changing the data reuse culture and could support research data object with its digital research data infrastructure. Therefore, it is vital to align digitalization goals with the needs of an open, reusable, and reproducible science perspective. The recommendations developed might help institutions who embrace

heterogeneous research communities with different requirements of research data management and sharing.

References

- [1] Küsters, U., & Klages, T. (2018). Fostering Open Science at Fraunhofer. <https://dspacecris.eurocris.org/handle/11366/644>
- [2] Küsters, U., & Erben-Russ, M. (2012). Forschungsinformationssysteme bei Fraunhofer. FORSCHUNGSINFORMATION IN DEUTSCHLAND: ANFORDERUNGEN, STAND UND NUTZEN EXISTIERENDER FORSCHUNGSINFORMATIONSSYSTEME, 37. http://www.forschungsinform.de/Publikationen/Download/working_paper_10_2012.pdf
- [3] Otto, B., Auer, S., Cirullies, J., Jürjens, J., Menz, N., Schon, J., & Wenzel, S. (2016). Industrial data space: digital sovereignty over data. Fraunhofer White Paper. <https://www.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/zv/en/fields-of-research/industrial-data-space/whitepaper-industrial-data-space-eng.pdf>
- [4] Otto, B., et al. "Reference architecture model for the Industrial Data Space." Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, Munich (2017). https://www.fit.fraunhofer.de/content/dam/fit/en/documents/Industrial-Data-Space_Reference-Architecture-Model-2017.pdf
- [5] Ammann, N., Nielsen, L. H., Peters, C. S., & de Smaele, T. M. (2011). DataCite metadata schema for the publication and citation of research data. <http://doi.org/10.5438/0012>
- [6] DSpace 6.x Documentation: <https://wiki.duraspace.org/display/DSDOC6x/DSpace+6.x+Documentation> [Accessed July 10. 2018]
- [7] Palmer, D. T., Bollini, A., Mornati, S., & Mennielli, M. (2014). DSpace-CRIS@ HKU: Achieving visibility with a CERIF compliant open source system. Procedia Computer Science, 33, 118-123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2014.06.019>
- [8] Chakrabarti, A., Quix, C., Geisler, S., Pullmann, J., Khromov, A., & Jarke, M. Goal-Oriented Modelling of Relations and Dependencies in Data Marketplaces. http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2118/iStar2018_paper_4.pdf
- [9] Quix, C., Hai, R., & Vatov, I. (2016). GEMMS: A Generic and Extensible Metadata Management System for Data Lakes. In CAiSE Forum (pp. 129-136). <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1612/paper17.pdf>
- [10] Wilkinson, M. D., Sansone, S. A., Schultes, E., Doorn, P., da Silva Santos, L. O. B., & Dumontier, M. (2018). A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness. Scientific data, 5. doi: [10.1038/sdata.2018.118](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.118)